

The First Law of Thermodynamics and the Abstraction to a Lack of Information in a Deterministic System

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In (1), we argued that one may use the first law of thermodynamics, along with the Sackur-Tetrode equation, ideal gas law and $PV = nRt$ to describe a deterministic particle bouncing elastically in a 1-dimensional box such that the size of the box changes by dL . We point out that (2) introduces this same idea, in a slightly different manner, and so we wish to analyze the scenario in more detail.

Given that this is a deterministic problem, what actually happens is described by Newtonian physics, i.e. a particle has work done on it Fdx which changes its kinetic energy $d(p^2/2m)$. This leads to $dE = d(\text{change in kinetic energy}) = Fdx$ which is certainly not the first law of thermodynamics. $dE = Fdx$, however, requires a knowledge of $x(t)$ as the work happens in some dx region at some time. If one abstracts the problem, i.e. deliberately disregards information about this deterministic problem, one may argue that the particle is bouncing back and forth in a box of length L . In such a scenario, energy is still $p^2/2m$ and $dE = d(p^2/2m)$, but there is entropy because one does not know where the particle is at any time. This leads also to the notion of pressure on average and that p may change internally or at the wall. As seen in (1), this abstraction changes $dE = Fdx$ into $dE = TdS - PdV$, even though physically the latter arises only due to a lack of information and not any physical randomness in the problem. Thus, an inherently deterministic problem may have some information removed and be described in a statistical manner even though there is no randomness in the problem.

Deterministic Problem Described by the First Law of Thermodynamics

In (1), we considered the case of a particle with kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ which is acted on by a force in a Newtonian manner. Then

$$dE = d(p^2/2m) = F dx \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is clearly not the first law of thermodynamics. In (1), we noted that if the particle is in a box of length L , then one could try to consider the change in momentum to be linked to an internal energy change in the box without any work at the wall, or solely to work at the wall.

For work done at the wall: $dE = -P dL$ (where P is pressure) as written in (1).

On the other hand, if no work is done at the wall, a change in momentum may be considered due to an internal change in energy (as argued in (1)) i.e.

$$dE = d(\text{no work (i.e. no } -PdV)) = d \text{ function}(T,L) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Here } E = \frac{1}{2} T = p^2/2m \quad ((3))$$

We then went on to show that one may find the no work function in ((2)) to be equivalent to $T dS$ with $T = p/p_0$ and S consistent with the Sackur-Tetrode equation. In other words, one could consider a deterministic scenario of a particle in a box and by losing information about $x(t)$ describe the situation using the first law of thermodynamics, the Sackur-Tetrode equation, ideal gas law $E = \frac{1}{2} T$ and $PL = nRT$.

Alternative Approach of (2)

We note that (2) has recently described the same problem in a very similar manner. (2) uses:

$v = \text{velocity} = dH/dp$ where H is energy E (Hamiltonian) ((4))

$v/l = \text{frequency of the particle hitting the wall}$ ((5))

$d(p/l) = p dl + l dp$ ((6))

Multiplying by v/l yields: $v/l d(p/l) = vp/l dl + v dp = vp/l dl + dE$ ((7))

((7)) has the look of the first law of thermodynamics, especially if one identifies:

$vp dl/l$ with $Pdl = nRT/l dl$ with $T = p/p_0$ and $nR=1$ so $Pdl = p/p_0 dl/l = pv dl/l$ ((8))

This means that $v/l d(p/l)$ has the sense of TdS .

The point we make, however, is that a particle bouncing back and forth in a box of size l is deterministic. In order to use statistical ideas, one must make the problem statistical and we suggest that means losing information even if ultimately that information exists and the problem is deterministic.

Analysis of the Problem

As stated above,

$dE = d(p^2/2m) = F dx$ ((9))

A particle which has its p changed is Newtonian and there is no First Law of thermodynamics. This view, however, requires following the particle in time, i.e. knowing

$x(t)$ ((10))

Without the knowledge of ((10)), one cannot possibly use ((9)) because the force acts in a certain dx region in a time interval dt . If one considers an ensemble of particles in boxes of l with

p, then one might imagine that one does not know $x(t)$ and so has no idea when or where p changes. It might change due to the box length changing or there might be an internal change. Now the problem is no longer Newtonian due to a deliberate loss of information and the separation of an energy change to two possibilities instead of a single Fdx . The energy change is still:

$$dE = p dp / m \quad ((11))$$

We suggest considering the Sackur-Tetrode equation for entropy, $-PdV$ with $PV = nRT$ and $E = .5 nRT$ with $n=1$ $R=1$ for 1-dimension. One may see that in the case of:

$$PdV = T/V dV \quad \text{and} \quad E = .5 p^2/m = .5 T \quad \text{that} \quad PdV = p dp / m = 1/V dV \quad ((11))$$

One no longer has the simple $dE = F dV$.

The Sackur-Tetrode equation ((3)) is:

$$S/N = \ln(V/N (2\pi E)^{3/2}) + 5/2 \quad \text{so with } N=1 \quad ((12))$$

$$TdS = T (d \ln(V) + .5 d \ln(E)) \quad ((13))$$

The first term on the RHS is linked to PdV and the second to $1/T dE$.

Thus, one may mathematically describe $dE = d p^2/2m$ by two terms, $- PdV$ and $T dS$. If one gives up the notion of following $x(t)$, then it seems that these two math terms are linked with statistical uncertainty in space and the exact mechanism needed to change momentum p. In other words, one takes a completely deterministic system and deliberately throws away information (which could be measured) and then describes it in a classical statistical mechanical manner.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) we argued that a completely deterministic system of a single particle with momentum p bouncing elastically in a 1-dimensional box of size V could have its p changed in a Newtonian manner. If, however, one deliberately throws away knowledge of $x(t)$, then one may describe the system using statistical mechanical ideas by considering an internal p change or a change due the length V changing (at the wall). This leads to math which is consistent with $dE = d p^2/2m$ as shown in (1). We note that recently (2) have considered the same example, albeit in a slightly different manner and have also obtained the first law of thermodynamics.

We try to show here that it is the deliberate disregard for information and not any inherent randomness or probability in the deterministic system which allows it to be described by classical statistical mechanics. Thus, it is possible for a statistical mechanical description to be applied to a completely deterministic situation if one has lost some information.

References

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